

EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS ON THE CYCLIC BEHAVIOUR OF ALUMINIUM FUSIBLE LINKS

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Abstract: *The research activity presented in this paper is part of the European Research Fund for Coal and Steel project entitled “Fire and Seismic performances of Hybrid fireWALLs in case of single-storey industrial and commercial steel buildings”. The aim of the project is to design a hybrid firewall solution using sandwich panels for single-storey buildings connected with the unprotected steel structure by means of fusible links, made of aluminium bolts. In case of a fire event, the fusible link system will rapidly lose strength disconnecting the steelwork from the firewall; thus, it will preserve the part of the building not affected by fire. Considering that buildings can be located in seismic prone regions, it is essential to verify that the system can withstand earthquake forces without losing stability. On these premises, this paper shows part of the results of an experimental campaign aimed at characterising the seismic behaviour of different fusible link details, that connect the steelwork with the firewall. In particular, preliminary numerical analyses performed on existing case studies of single-storey steel buildings located in low and moderate seismicity zones are shown and they were used to estimate the seismic forces acting on the fusible links. The design of two details, that differ from the presence of sandwich panels, to be tested in the laboratory is presented. The outcomes of the tests under monotonic and cyclic loading as well as the numerical calibration with nonlinear elements are thoroughly described.*

1. Introduction

The structural performance of fire walls has been widely investigated in many research projects, as for example by Russo S. and Sciarretta F. (2013), and by Hopkin D. J. and Al. (2012). In particular, fire walls made of masonry concrete or gypsum plasterboard in multi-storey building or low-rise single storey building were investigated. Typically, isolated fire walls are considered that implies neglecting any interaction with the main structural members. Guidelines and recommendations about their own structure and foundation are provided, in Simms W. I. and Newman G. M. (2002), and in Bennetts I.D. and O. Meagher A.J. (1995): solutions that in case of a high-rise single-storey building could be economically unreasonable. In this context, the European Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) FISHWALL project was funded with the aim to analyse the fire and seismic performance of hybrid steel-based fire wall solutions using sandwich panels in single-storey steel buildings, connected to the main structure by means of fusible links, made of aluminium bolts. The innovative proposal investigated in the current project concerns the possibility to use lightweight steel-faced sandwich panels as fire walls connected to the main structure through fusible links, that are made of aluminium bolts, as schematically shown in Figure 1. In this perspective, the fire solution is also investigated under seismic loading,

to obtain a suitable solution for structures located in low and in moderate seismicity zones so that to guarantee the stability of the wall during a seismic event.

Figure 1. Scheme of a possible connection solution between the fire wall and the steel structure.

The paper is organized as follow: Section 2 briefly introduces the numerical analysis on selected single storey buildings under seismic action to evaluate the range of seismic forces in the fusible links; Section 3 shows the design of two details to be experimentally tested; Section 4 illustrates the results of the experimental tests, whereas the calibration of nonlinear numerical models is reported in Section 5. Finally, in Section 6 the conclusions and the future perspectives are reported.

2. Seismic analyses on selected steel buildings

2.1. Case studies

In order to estimate the forces in the fusible links induced by a seismic event, several numerical analyses were run on selected steel buildings. All investigated case studies are characterised by two lateral-resisting systems along the two main directions; that is a recurring solution in single-storey industrial halls. In detail, portal frames in one principal direction and bracing systems in the other direction. To estimate the force on the fusible link elements, different arrangements both of the firewall and fusible links were investigated. Four case studies were selected and Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics of the structures.

Table 1 Main characteristics of the portal frames and area of the selected case studies.

Case study 1	Case study 2	Case study 3	Case study 4
Hot rolled steel profiles	Hot rolled steel profiles	Welded sections steel profiles	Welded sections steel profiles
Single-bay portal frame	Two-bay portal frame	Two-bay portal frame	Four-bay portal frame
1400 m ²	3100 m ²	6000 m ²	12000 m ²

For each case study, the following 2 different seismic locations were taken into account:

- region with low seismicity level characterised by peak ground acceleration (PGA) = 0.04 g;
- region with moderate seismicity level characterised by peak ground acceleration (PGA) = 0.12 g.

The finite element software SAP2000 (Computers and Structures, 2003) was used to develop 3D numerical models. In particular, two firewall positions were investigated: the firewall is placed either parallel or orthogonal to the steel portal frames, as illustrated in Figure 2 **Error! Reference source not found.** Linear dynamic analyses with response spectrum according to EN 1998-1 (CEN, Eurocode 8, 2005) were performed and to estimate an upper boundary of the forces acting on the fusible links, the behaviour factor was considered equal to 1.5. The response spectra were computed in both horizontal directions as well as in the vertical direction. The elastic response spectra for the two seismic regions considered are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Numerical 3D models of two case studies with: a) the fire wall parallel and b) perpendicular to the portal frames.

Figure 3. Horizontal design response spectra with 5% equivalent damping.

2.2. Results of the analysis

For brevity, in Table 2 the main results for two case studies are reported out of a total of 20 analyses. In particular, Case study 4 located in a moderate seismicity region, with the fire wall orthogonal to portal frames, as well as Case study 1 located in a low seismicity region, with the fire wall orthogonal to portal frames. These two case studies provided the largest forces on the fusible links for the two seismicity levels.

Table 2 Maximum shear value in the fusible links.

Seismicity level	With roof	Without roof
Moderate	179.37 kN	153.67 kN
Low	70.55 kN	80.04 kN

Considering that some modelling assumptions were simplified, in order to obtain more realistic results, for Case study 4, a finite element model was developed considering the bracing system with a tension diagonal model, i.e. only the diagonal in tension was modelled, whereas the diagonal in compression was assumed to elastically buckle in accordance with the actual design. With this behaviour of the bracing system, a general increase of the forces in the fusible links was noted as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Comparison of the shear value in the fusible links.

Model	Simplified model	Tension diagonal model
Without roof	153.67 kN	182.12 kN

3. Design of the seismic details

Based on the results of the numerical analyses, a series of laboratory tests were designed. All the details were conceived for the fire and seismic action. Figure 4 **Error! Reference source not found.** shows the two final configurations of the details that connect the fire wall to the steel structure taken as a reference. In both of them the aluminium bolts (in red) are subjected to shear. In Figure 4b, the fusible links are connected to the main steelwork by means of secondary structural elements, whereas the detail presented in Figure 4a, C and Z elements are interposed between the fire wall and the building columns. In both cases, the fire wall is perpendicular to the portal frames. Then, considering the wide range of results obtain by the numerical analysis, the largest forces in shear were considered during the design of the seismic tests, i.e. 80 kN for low seismicity and 180 kN for moderate seismicity, as shown in Table 2.

Figure 4. Plan view of the reference details

M16 and M12 aluminium bolts were employed. In Table 4 and in Table 5, the shear resistance values calculated in accordance with EN 1999-1-1 (CEN, Eurocode 9, 2007) ($F_{v,Rd,EN1999}$) are shown, where the bolt is classified as “AlZn5,5MgCu” (7075) according to ISO 209, with a nominal ultimate tensile strength f_u taken equal to 490 MPa. Moreover, the experimental shear strength ($F_{v,Rd,TESTS}$) is also reported.

Table 4 M16 shear resistance.

α_v	F_{ub}	A_s	γ_{M2}	$F_{v,Rd,EN1999}$	$F_{v,Rd,TESTS}$
[-]	[MPa]	[mm ²]	[-]	[kN]	[kN]
0.5	490	157	1.25	30.77	79.00

Table 5 M12 shear resistance.

α_v	F_{ub}	A_s	γ_{M2}	$F_{v,Rd,EN1999}$	$F_{v,Rd,TESTS}$
[-]	[MPa]	[mm ²]	[-]	[kN]	[kN]
0.5	490	84.3	1.25	16.52	36.56

Table 6 reports the number of bolts necessary for the two different seismicity levels. Moreover, to have symmetric details, the number of bolts was increased.

Table 6 Number of aluminium bolts.

Level of seismicity	Shear force [kN]	n. M16 required/used	n. M12 required/used
Moderate	179.37	6	11/12
Low	80.04	3/4	5/6

On these premises, a total of six details were designed. For brevity, in this work only two details, namely Detail 4 and Detail 5 are thoroughly presented. They are derived from the reference detail shown in Figure 4b. The details were designed according to the structural standards in force. Moreover, numerical analyses were

conducted up to failure by means of the IdeaStatica software (StatiCa, I. D. E. A., 2021) to have a more accurate estimation of the actual forces and modes of collapse of the specimens (Pasquali, S., Tondini, N. and Zanon, G., 2023).

Figure 5 and Figure 6 show two of the six details above mentioned, while Table 7 and Table 8 report the elements composing the details.

Figure 5. Detail 4. a) Front view and b) lateral view.

Figure 6. Detail 5. a) Front view and b) lateral view..

Table 7. Elements composing Detail 4. Dimensions in mm.

UPN element	T element – plate 1	T element – plate 2	Aluminium bolts	Steel rods
4 UPN160	2 190x180x10	2 190x180x15	6 M12	8 M16 10.9

Table 8. Elements composing Detail 5. Dimensions in mm.

UPN element	T element – plate 1	T element – plate 2	Aluminium bolts	Steel bolts
4 UPN160	2 190x180x10	2 190x180x15	6 M12	4 M16 8.8

The specimens were tested using hydraulic actuator of 1000 kN with a stroke ± 250 mm positioned in a reaction frame, as shown in Figure 7. On each detail, strain gauges and displacement transducers were applied to record the deformation state and the local displacement of the fusible links, as reported in Figure 8. Both monotonic and cyclic test were performed, cyclic tests according to the ECCS protocol (ECCS publication n°45, 1986).

Figure 7. Test setup.

a)

b)

Figure 8. Specimen instrumentation: a) displacement transducers and b) strain-gauges

Table 9 summarizes the configurations and the type of tests that are to be tested in the laboratory. As mentioned before, for brevity on the experimental outcomes of Detail 4 and 5 will be described.

Table 9 Experimental programme.

	Design seismicity	Bolts	Tests
Detail 1	Low (80 kN)	M12	2 monotonic 2 cyclic
Detail 2	Moderate (180 kN)	M16	2 monotonic 2 cyclic
Detail 3.1	Moderate (180 kN)	M16	2 monotonic 2 cyclic
Detail 3.2	Moderate (180 kN)	M12	2 monotonic 2 cyclic
Detail 4	Moderate (180 kN)	M12	2 monotonic 2 cyclic
Detail 5	Moderate (180 kN)	M12	2 monotonic 2 cyclic

4. Experimental tests

As introduced in 3, all the details designed were tested following the ECCS procedure. The ECCS procedure was conceived to investigate the structural behaviour of steel components under cyclic loading. As reported in Table 9, in the experimental campaign, two monotonic tests and two cyclic tests were performed. In greater detail since the details are not symmetric, two monotonic tests in tension and compression were carried out. By means of these outcomes the displacements at yielding e_y for tension and compression were selected and the cyclic protocol was derived. Considering all the specimens, the laboratory campaign started with Detail 4 and Detail 5 due to their complex setup. All the tests were carried out in displacement control with different displacement rate depending on the test.

4.1. Detail 4 test results

The results of the two monotonic tests, one in tension and one in compression, are shown in Figure 9 **Error! Reference source not found.**. The several peaks in both the force-displacement curves are related to the progressive failure of one or multiple aluminium bolt shear planes. Indeed, due to the deformations caused by the presence of the sandwich panels (see Figure 10), additional and different in magnitude, depending on the bolt position, secondary forces were generated in the fusible links in terms of horizontal shear. As a consequence, the maximum capacity did not reach the design force. The instrumentation arranged on the specimens, especially the strain-gauges that were located to record horizontal strains close to the aluminium bolts, showed strain measures in accordance with the outcomes.

Figure 9. a) Monotonic test results and b) ECCS displacement history.

a)

b)

Figure 10. a) Detail 4 at failure and b) aluminium bolts after the tension test.

In **Error! Reference source not found.** the e_y parameters chosen to derive the displacement history for the cyclic tests are highlighted for the parts in tension and compression. Due to the brittle behaviour of the detail and, therefore, the difficulty in defining the precise e_y as described in the procedure document, it was selected the first failure of the aluminium bolts as the yielding displacement. Considering the similar behaviour obtained in tension and compression, the same point was selected for both tests, as can be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.**

The results of two cyclic tests in terms of force-displacement are shown in Figure 11. Moreover, the two monotonic curves were superimposed.

Figure 11. Results of cyclic tests in comparison with the monotonic tests.

Despite the brittle behaviour of the detail, a hysteretic behaviour can be observed. The failure of the detail occurred, in both the cyclic tests, during the reloading to the e_y displacement. Also in this case, the aluminium bolts collapsed progressively. The comparison between the two monotonic tests shows a good agreement in particular with the compression branch, while some differences could be noticed in the tension part owing to the inherent variability of the experimental tests.

4.2. Detail 5 test results

Detail 5 is the same as of Detail 4 but for the absence of the sandwich panels (see Figure 12a). Such an arrangement determined an increase in stiffness and capacity of the detail. In fact, no secondary forces established in the fusible links that, as confirmed by the readings of the instrumentation, were subjected by basically only vertical shear. The results of the two monotonic tests, one in tension and one in compression, are presented in Figure 13a. The several peaks shown by both the force-displacement curves are related again to the progressive failure of one or more aluminium bolt shear planes (Figure 12b). However, since the loading was more symmetric, higher forces were reached compared with Detail 4. It is worth noting that the two monotonic curves are considerably different because of a different tightening procedure of specimen to the actuator. For the remaining specimens the same tightening procedure was followed. Thus, global behaviour of the specimen was not symmetric in tension and in compression and two different yielding displacements, corresponding to the first failure of the aluminium bolts, were selected for the cyclic tests, as shown in red in Figure 13Error! Reference source not found..

Figure 12. a) Detail 5 at failure and b) aluminium bolts after the tension test.

Figure 13. a) Monotonic test results and b) ECCS displacement history.

Figure 14. Results of cyclic tests in comparison with the monotonic tests.

The results of the two cyclic tests are shown in Figure 14. Despite the brittle response of the detail, a hysteretic behaviour can be observed. The failure of the details occurred, in both the cyclic tests, during the reloading to the e_y displacement. In this case, again, the aluminium bolts collapsed progressively. The comparison between the two monotonic tests shows a good agreement in particular on the tension branch, while a difference may be noticed on the compression part because of the different bolt tightening procedure.

5. Numerical models

As described in the introduction, to perform seismic global analyses, an accurate modelling of the hysteretic behaviour of the details tested is needed. In this respect, a numerical model was developed by means the OpenSees software (McKenna, F., Fenves, G. L, and Scott, M. H. (2000)). The calibration of the joints represents an important step to investigate the seismic response of the buildings by nonlinear dynamic analyses.

5.1. Detail 4 calibration

Figure 15 shows the schematic representation of Detail 4 for the calibration process. As can be seen, the behaviour of the whole joint was calibrated. For convenience, the model included two nonlinear elements arranged in parallel way, i.e. nonlinear element for each aluminium bolted detail. The material model used to describe the inelastic behaviour was a Pinching4 hysteretic model that allowed for modelling the slip due to the bolt-hole clearance, as well as the stiffness and strength degradation occurred during the tests.

Figure 15. Numerical model of Detail 4

Figure 16 shows the comparison between experimental and numerical relationships in terms of force–displacement curves of all the tested joints subjected to the same ECCS loading protocol. The hysteretic behaviour model was developed performing a static analysis in displacement control, using the same displacement history as for the experimental tests. Good agreement in terms of strength and stiffness may be observed.

Figure 16. Detail 4: numerical vs. experimental force-displacement comparison.

In terms of dissipated energy, reported in Table 10, computed as the sum of areas underlying the force-displacement curves, it is possible to observe that, as expected, the low values of energy, as well as some difference between the two cyclic tests. Moreover, a good agreement between experimental and numerical results may be observed with an error in the order of 10 %.

Table 10 Comparison of dissipated energy between experimental and numerical results.

Specimen	Protocol	Experimental [J]	Numerical [J]	Error
Detail 4	ECCS cyclic -1	3504	3952	-12.8 %
Detail 4	ECCS cyclic -2	4271	3952	7.47 %

5.2. Detail 5 calibration

Figure 17 shows the schematic representation of Detail 5 for the calibration process that followed the same procedure as of Detail 4, that exploited the Pinching4 material to model the nonlinearities.

Figure 17. Numerical model of Detail 5

Figure 18 shows the comparison between experimental and numerical relationships in terms of force–displacement curves of all the tested joints subjected to the same ECCS loading protocol. Again, good agreement in terms of strength and stiffness may be observed.

Figure 18. Detail 5: numerical vs. experimental force-displacement comparison.

In terms of dissipated energy, very good agreement between the numerical and experimental force–displacement curves can be appreciated, as reported in Table 11, with an error of about 3 %.

Table 11 Comparison of dissipated energy between experimental and numerical results.

Specimen	Protocol	Experimental [J]	Numerical [J]	Error
Detail 5	ECCS cyclic -1	2451	2381	2.87 %
Detail 5	ECCS cyclic -2	2339	2381	-1.77 %

6. Conclusions

This paper presented the results of experimental tests performed on two structural details, i.e. Detail 4 and 5, made of M12 aluminium bolts, conceived as fusible links, that are representative of the connection between the structural steelwork and hybrid fire walls in single-storey steel buildings. The details were designed under moderate seismicity through linear dynamic analyses of the case studies with the aluminium bolts subjected to an estimated shear force of 180 kN. The two details are very similar but for the presence of the sandwich panels. To seismically characterize such details, both monotonic and cyclic tests were carried out. The behaviour of Detail 4 was affected by the presence of the sandwich panels whose deformation induced secondary horizontal shear forces in the aluminium bolts. As a result, the aluminium bolts failed progressively

limiting the overall capacity of the detail. Conversely, Detail 5 exhibited higher stiffness and strength with failure that involved more bolts at once. The model calibration of the two details were performed and agrees well with the experimental evidence. The calibrated numerical models of the fusible links will be used then to perform global nonlinear seismic analyses on the 3D model of case studies. Moreover, the end of the experimental programme that includes 4 more details will be finalized.

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8. References

Bennetts I.D. and O. Meagher A.J., *Single Storey Steel-framed Buildings: Support of External Walls in Fire*, BHP Structural Steel Development Group, Technical Note No.1, Australia, 1995.

CEN, Eurocode 8: Design of structures for earthquake resistance. Part 1-1: General rules, seismic actions and rules for building, 2005.

CEN, Eurocode 9: Design of aluminium structures. Part 1-1: General structural rules, 2007.

Computers and Structures (2003), "SAP2000: Integrated Software for Structural Analysis and Design", Computers and Structures, Inc. (<http://csiberkeley.com>), Berkeley, CA, U.S.A.

ECCS, Recommended Testing Procedure for Assessing the Behaviour of Structural Steel Elements under Cyclic Loads, ECCS Publication n° 45; ECCS: Bruxelles, 1986.

Hopkin D. J. and Al., A numerical study of gypsum plasterboard behaviour under standard and natural fire conditions, *Fire and Materials*, Volume 36, issue N°2, pp. 107-126, 2012.

ISO, ISO 209:2007 specifies the designations indicating the chemical composition of aluminium and aluminium alloys, 2007.

McKenna, F., Fenves, G. L, and Scott, M. H. (2000) Open System for Earthquake Engineering Simulation. University of California, Berkeley, <http://opensees.berkeley.edu>.

Pasquali, S., Tondini, N. and Zanon, G. (2023), Seismic characterization of aluminium fusible links in single-storey steel buildings. *Proceedings of EUROSTEEL 2023*, Amsterdam, 12-14 September, *ce/papers*, 6: 1275-1280.

Russo S. and Sciaretta F., Masonry exposed to high temperatures: Mechanical behaviour and properties — an overview, *Fire Safety Journal*, volume 55, pp 69-86, 2013.

Simms W. I. and Newman G. M., SCI publication P313: Single-storey steel framed building in fire boundary conditions, The Steel Construction Institute, 2002.

StatiCa, I. D. E. A. (2021). IDEA StatiCa connection. V, 20(5115), 1.